

**DR. EMIL MAYER'S RESIGNATION AS AMERICAN EDITOR
OF THE CENTRALBLATT.***

40 East Forty-first Street,
New York, Aug. 5th, 1915.

To the Editor of the Laryngoscope:

Dear Sir:—The Editor and the Publisher of Semon's *Internationales Centralblatt für Laryngologie* have removed the name of Sir Felix Semon from the title page of their Journal, where it had been placed in honor at the time of his retirement from active practice six years ago, because, as a naturalized English citizen, he expressed his indignation at "Germany's barbarous warfare."

Since this action destroyed the Journal's claim to be international in character, and as a protest against the introduction of politics in a scientific Journal, as also in loyalty to one who has done so much for Laryngology, I promptly tendered my resignation as collaborator for America to that Journal, for silence on my part might be construed as an endorsement of their action.

As the matter is of interest to all American Laryngologists, may I ask you to publish this statement with the accompanying copy of my letter to the Editor and Publisher, which is fully explanatory, at an early date?

Yours very truly,
(Signed) EMIL MAYER.

40 East Forty-first Street, New York City.

Prof. Dr. G. Finder, Editor,

Mr. August Hirschwald, Publisher,

*International Centralblatt für Laryngologie, Rhinologie,
Berlin, Germany.*

Gentlemen:—In the June number of the *Centralblatt* I find the following:

"1. Declaration.

"In the *Times* of the twelfth ultimo there is an open letter of Sir Felix Semon, as follows:

To the Editor of the Times:

Sir: For many years I believed in the possibility of a better understanding between this country and Germany, and it was the most bitter disappointment to me when the great crash came last year. Even then I hoped that it would suffice for a naturalized British citizen of German

NOTE—Drs. McBride, Logan Turner, H. J. Davis and Watson Williams, of England, and Dr. E. Schmiegelow, of Copenhagen, have also resigned from the "Centralblatt" for the same reason as Dr. Emil Mayer.

extraction loyally to do his duty by his adopted country without making any public expression of his faith. The inhuman methods of German warfare, however, have often, and of late with ever increasing force, induced me to think that it would be right for a German by birth to publicly express his detestation of that policy. What has hitherto deterred me from doing so has been the fear that such a statement might be misconstrued as a desire to personally court favor. But now that Sir Arthur Pinero, in the letter published in the *Times* of to-day, has pointed out that an attitude of continued silence might be interpreted as "Sitting on the Gate," I beg to say that I emphatically abhor the barbarous methods, one and all, employed by Germany.

Yours obediently,
FELIX SEMON.

Rignalls, Great Missenden, May 11:

When Sir Felix Semon, surely misled by the lying reports in the press of the enemies of Germany, wrote this letter taking a public stand against the land of his birth, he must have known that this would create the deepest pain and bitterest disappointment to his German friends and colleagues. Wise and foreseeing as he is, he could not feel for an instant any doubt of the effect this would have on any further relations connecting him with the Old Fatherland.

He could not doubt that these consequences would affect his relations with this *Centralblatt* which he founded, edited for a quarter of a century, and brought to its fullest bloom, and which in memory thereof still bears his name. Although this journal is an international one, recording the scientific labors of our specialty in all lands, always keeping most carefully its international character, it nevertheless remains the fact that it appears in the German language and in the capital city of the German Empire.

Because of this fact the editor and publisher, proud to be Germans, consider it to be further impossible to retain at the head of this journal the name of a man who has in a public statement attacked their Fatherland and hence, to their great regret, still grateful for Semon's labors in this journal, are compelled to declare that the name of Semon in the title of the *International Centralblatt* will henceforth be omitted."

(Signed)

GEORGE FINDER, Editor.
AUGUST HIRSCHWALD, Publisher.

This combined act of yours has affected me most seriously, and I trust that I may briefly recall to you my connection with the *Centralblatt*, which I feel gives me the right to express my opinion of your action.

It is just sixteen years ago this month that Sir Felix Semon appointed me as independent editor of the *Centralblatt* for America, in association with Professor Lefferts, with whom I worked in entire harmony for ten years, until upon Semon's withdrawal from all active work, Lefferts resigned, while I remained at Semon's urgent and earnest request as sole American editor.

During these ten years, there sprung up between Sir Felix Semon and myself the strongest bonds of friendship, and you are aware that it was at my instigation, and as a result of my labors that a beautiful silver box, a replica of a bound volume of the *Centralblatt*, was presented to him on behalf of the past and present collaborators on the occasion of his retirement from active work in 1909.

This box, made by Tiffany of New York, bore the words of Prof. A. Rosenberg, of Berlin, after the name of the donors: "In love and honor as a token of their recognition of the valuable services to laryngology and in grateful remembrance of the most friendly consideration shown to each one of them by Sir Felix Semon."

You are also aware that in this long series of sixteen years, I have subscribed for journals in order to make abstracts conveniently, that much of the material was typewritten for me, and that all these expenses, including the postage, was borne by me, and the only return I received was a copy of the *Centralblatt*, together with the knowledge that the work of my fellow-countrymen was fully represented in the *World's Literature*.

Since your editorship, I have been the sole representative of America, and you will agree that now, as before, America has led all countries in the yearly count of abstracts published. You know also that in the sixteen years of my work no complaint of unfairness has been registered against my work, either to you or to myself.

With this explanatory preamble, I feel that I have shown my loyalty to you and to the Centralblatt, and am thereby entitled to express myself regarding your action in removing the name of Semon from the title page of the journal.

I feel that the right was not yours to take this drastic action without conferring with those most deeply concerned, your co-editors, with whom you are in regular communication. I furthermore disapprove of what you have done and also protest most forcibly against the publication of your patriotic and political views in a purely scientific journal.

In your attempt to cast obloquy on the name of a man who stands easily the highest of all living laryngologists, a courteous gentleman and a faithful friend, you leave me no other course which I can follow in honor and self-respect than to tender my resignation as American collaborator to the International Centralblatt for Laryngologie, to take effect immediately and which I now formally do.

I shall at once notify the American publishers of books and journals, heretofore sent me for review, that I have resigned and am no longer entitled to receive them.

Regretting deeply that your action has forced me to take this summary method of severing our heretofore cordial relations, I am,

Yours very truly,

(Signed)

EMIL MAYER.

Roentgenography of the Maxillary Antrum. N. S. FINZI and G. S. HETT, *Arch. Radiol. and Electrother.*, V. 20, No. 2, July, 1915.

In the x-ray examination of the maxillary antrum the following points should be borne in mind: (a) prolonged screen examination may cause epilation; (b) a distance of twenty inches of the anticathode from the nearest point on the scalp is best; (c) the anterior view is most important and the oblique view is also of importance because it shows the associated teeth; (d) when the air in the antrum is replaced by liquid or solid matter the antrum appears darker. Marked opacity means thickening of the bony wall of the antrum. Diagnosis should not be based on x-ray examination alone, but the symptoms and physical signs as evidenced by anterior and posterior rhinoscopy, and transillumination should be taken into consideration.

Ed.